

Effects of Extreme Mirror Downscaling on Open Micro-Fabry–Perot Spectral Responses and Resonant Mode Profiles

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This article revisits fundamentals of Fabry–Pérot cavities, addressing limits of extreme miniaturization and consequences. More specifically, both the spectral responses and the mode profiles are found to be gradually affected by the size reduction of the cavity mirrors with respect to spot size of an incident optical Gaussian beam. A fully analytical methodology accounting for the finite borders of the cavity is proposed to predict the behavior. Severe consequences of miniaturization appear on the spectral response and in the spatial distribution of the resonant modes, with degradation of the quality factors, typically down to 665 for mirrors of $77 \times 150 \mu\text{m}$, while it should be 2407 for their macroscopic counterparts of equivalent cavity length of $210 \mu\text{m}$ and reflectance $R = 70\%$. The observed deviations from the well-established Fabry–Pérot models are quantified and ascribed to imperfect mode confinement due to the finite mirror's dimensions. Validation of the modeling approach is given by comparing with experimental data obtained on microfabricated silicon cavities and another comparison with asymptotic values where analytical equations still apply. This work aims contributing to better assessment of microscale cavities used in photothermal and photoacoustic spectroscopy, in optofluidic devices for refractometry, biochemical, and gas sensing.

spectroscopic gas sensing technologies such as photothermal spectroscopy^[17–23] and photoacoustic spectroscopy^[24–27] Both techniques are favorable to extreme miniaturization, contrary to absorption spectroscopy. Therefore, the use of open microscale FP cavities is advantageous. Other applications of open micro-FP cavities include fluid sensing,^[28–31] micro flowmeter,^[32] accelerometers,^[33] pressure sensors,^[34,35] seawater salinity monitoring,^[36] strain sensor,^[37] and various sensors and interferometers based on the Vernier effect.^[38–40]

In most of those applications, the system performance is dependent on the finesse of the FP response. The design and modeling for FP cavities was thoroughly investigated in literature,^[41–44] including discussion on their stability^[45,46] and their optical characterization.^[47,48] However, contrary to macroscopic FP cavities, the extreme reduction of the micro-FP mirror's dimensions X and Y can lead to ultimate limits in which it

becomes close or comparable to the spot size w_0 . This situation is far from conventional FP cavities usually modeled as mirrors of infinite dimensions separated by a gap L . In this article, we revisit Fabry–Pérot formalism by considering the finite dimensions of the mirrors. We derive and implement *analytical* modeling that enables producing spectral responses and mode shapes. The analysis considers mirrors of cylindrical shapes, where their macroscopic counterparts are known to support Hermite–Gaussian resonant modes. **Figure 1** gives an illustration of the

1. Introduction

Microscale Fabry–Pérot (micro-FP) resonators with an empty gap are easily produced from silicon micromachining^[1–5] They are increasingly used as building blocks of photonic integrated devices and circuits based on free-space propagation of light, mainly in microcavity lasers,^[6,7] optical communication,^[1,8] refractometry^[9–14] optical trapping,^[15] and quantum information.^[16] They are expected to play a crucial role in emerging

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Figure 1. Typical architectures of empty FP cavities with a) planar and b) cylindrical mirrors, c,d) microscale FP cavities fabricated on silicon, where the cylindrical micromirrors are Bragg mirrors of one (three) silicon layers, respectively.

scope of this study. Figure 1a,b show typical architectures of empty FP cavities with planar and cylindrical mirrors, respectively. Figure 1c,d show such microscale FP cavities fabricated on silicon, where the cylindrical micromirrors are Bragg mirrors of one (three) silicon layers, respectively. The Bragg mirrors based on silicon–air stacks are intended to reach very high reflectance,^[1,2,49] while the cylindrical shape is intended to confine the electromagnetic field, hence minimizing the diffraction loss and enabling high quality factors.^[2,6,8,14] Notably, although spherical mirrors are more suitable than cylindrical mirrors to confine light and achieve stable FP cavities, they cannot be fabricated using conventional silicon micromachining such as reactive ion etching, which is by essence a directional etching of 2D patterns, leading to the extrusion of those patterns. When dealing with macroscopic FP cavities, based on the important assumption of big lateral dimensions (length and height) of the mirrors compared to the light spot size, the cylindrical FP cavities support Hermite–Gaussian modes, whose shapes and resonant wavelength are well-established from analytical formulae. Notably, in most practical cases, only the first even mode shapes are practically observable, typically modes TEM₀₀, TEM₂₀, and TEM₄₀, respectively. However, when considering miniaturized FP cavities, severe deviations from this ideal macroscopic scheme are observed. First, as the mirror’s lateral dimensions decrease, one can observe significant modifications on both the mode shape and the spectral response that will be addressed in this article thanks to the proposed analytical modeling methodology.

Another important impact of miniaturization is on the quality factor and finesse of the FP cavities. The quality factors of macroscopic FP cavities is governed solely by mirror’s reflectance R^{44}

$$Q = \frac{2\pi L}{\lambda_0} \left(\frac{\sqrt{R}}{1-R} \right) \quad (1)$$

However, in micro-FP cavities, the small mirror’s dimensions lead to severe diffraction losses. Considering the simple case of a Gaussian incident beam, its expansion when bouncing back and forth between the micromirrors eventually lead to a large portion of the beam to escape off the cavity, hence affecting the quality factor. Notably, the use of numerical tools for the analysis of micro-FP cavities cannot be practical. In the examples of micro-FP cavities shown in Figure 1c,d, the cavity has a length of 250 μm , the mirrors have a width of 200 μm and a height of 80 μm . Meshing of this domain with subwavelength pitch (say 0.1 μm) requires 4×10^9 elements and more nodes.

In what follows, we describe first the proposed modeling procedure, still based on analytical modeling, which is capable of addressing several issues arising from miniaturization. Second, we present the results obtained from this modeling strategy. In particular, the analysis considers gradual decrease of the dimensions and the corresponding impacts on resonance spectra. Our analysis also revealed severe implications on the mode profiles and quantitative evaluation of the quality factors accounting for diffraction losses. We also revisit the stability criteria of cylindrical FP cavities and corresponding implications on the spectral responses at the micro-scale. Notably, the model is validated through comparison with experimental data acquired on microscale FP cavities as well as the extreme case of macroscopic mirrors.

2. Results

In this section, we will present and discuss results obtained using the proposed model as well as some experimental observations related to FP miniaturization issues.

2.1. Impact of Miniaturization on the Modes’ Spatial Distribution and Spectral Response

In case of macroscopic mirrors of cylindrical shapes, the electric field distribution is obtained by solving Maxwell’s equations. The field takes the form of narrow beams, known as Hermite–Gaussian beams, fully described as follows in the general case of a mirror having curvatures along both the x -axis and the y -axis

$$E_{m,n}(x, y, z) = E_0 \frac{W_0}{W(z)} H_m \left[\sqrt{2} \frac{x}{W(z)} \right] H_n \left[\sqrt{2} \frac{y}{W(z)} \right] \times e^{-\frac{k^2 x^2 + y^2}{W^2(z)}} e^{-jkz - jk \frac{z^2 + y^2}{2R(z)} + j(m+n+1)\eta(z)} \quad (2)$$

In the particular case of a cylindrical mirror, only the curvature along the x -axis remains and Equation (2) reduces to

$$E_{m,0}(x, y, z) = E_0 \frac{W_0}{W(z)} H_m \left[\sqrt{2} \frac{x}{W(z)} \right] e^{-\frac{k^2 x^2 + y^2}{W^2(z)}} e^{-jkz - jk \frac{z^2 + y^2}{2R(z)} + j(m+1)\eta(z)} \quad (3)$$

This formulation translates into considering only the modes $(m, 0)$, where n always takes the value $n = 0$ (also corresponding to the 0th order function to take the value $H_0 = 1$ whatever the

position γ . Notably, for planar mirrors, the modes reduce to the fundamental Gaussian mode (0, 0), since there is no more curvature at all.

In this important part of our work, we investigate the effect of reducing the mirror lateral dimensions (height Y and width X) compared to the spot size ($2\omega_0$) of the incident beam. For this purpose, we proceed by varying gradually the mirror dimensions from the smallest size [$X = 4\omega_0$; $Y = 2\omega_0$], to the largest [$X = 10\omega_0$; $Y = 5\omega_0$]. While doing so, we can observe the gradual deviations from the Hermite–Gaussian distribution given in Equation (3), which holds true only for the largest mirrors dimensions where the results are shown in **Figure 2**. For each set of mirror’s dimensions, we can see the perturbations in the shape of the spatial distribution for modes TEM_{00} , TEM_{20} , and TEM_{40} . It is noted from the smallest mirrors that miniaturization can have a severe impact on the mode distribution if compared with the case of large mirrors.

Figure 2. Analysis of the consequences of gradual reduction of mirror’s dimensions X and Y , taking different values considering the light spot size ω_0 as a reference.

Figure 2 also shows the corresponding plots of the cavity spectral responses though the gradual reduction of mirror size. The obtained spectra differ not only in the positions of the resonant peaks and quality factors but they also reveal radically different behavior for the smallest dimensions. As a reminder, in case of macroscopic cavities with cylindrical mirrors of large dimensions with respect to the spot size, the resonance wavelengths for modes TEM_{mnq} can be obtained from a theoretical equation^[44,50]

$$v_{m,n,q} = \frac{c}{2n_0 n_r L} \left[q + (m + n + 1) \frac{\cos^{-1}(1 - \frac{L}{R})}{\pi} \right] \quad (4)$$

$$\lambda_{m,n,q} = c/v_{m,n,q} \quad (5)$$

where $v_{m,n,q}$ is the resonant frequency, m is the transverse mode order, q is the longitudinal mode order, the mode order n was taken equal to 0 as it is applicable only for spherical mirrors, c is the speed of light in free space, and $n_r = 1$ is the relative refraction index of the medium inside the cavity, which is air in this case. The cavity length is L , while R is the mirror’s radius of curvature.

It is worth mentioning that all results shown in Figure 2 are not accessible through direct theoretical predictions, neither through numerical calculations considering the huge number of nodes required for such simulations, hence the relevance of our modeling methodology is to highlight this kind of behaviour.

2.2. Quantitative Assessment on the FP Stability Criteria Translated into the Corresponding Spectral Responses

The stability condition of the cylindrical FP cavity is related to the values of its length L and mirror radius of curvature R

$$0 \leq \frac{L}{|R|} \leq 2 \quad (6)$$

Our modeling methodology enables more detailed qualitative and quantitative assessment of the gradual transition from stable to unstable cavities. This is illustrated in **Figure 3** in case of a cavity of length $L = 1000\mu\text{m}$ by varying the value of R from $300\mu\text{m}$ to $900\mu\text{m}$, given that R needs to be greater than or equal $500\mu\text{m}$ to stay stable according to Equation (6). On one hand, Figure 3a. shows the spectral response obtained from the model for $R < 500\mu\text{m}$ where the resulting response shows a weak quality factor and low transmittance indicating the behavior in case stability conditions are not met. On the other hand, Figure 3b shows the spectral responses for greater values of curvature $R \geq 500\mu\text{m}$. In this range, the cavity peaks are sharper and the spectral response is improved with increasing quality factor and transmittance. Also, it is observed that the resonance peaks are also little shifted. The latter is consistent with the theoretical prediction of the formula in Equation (4) which predicts that the resonant wavelength is dependent on the radius of curvature R .

2.3. Misalignment of the Spot with Respect to the FP Mirrors of Similar Dimensions

This section addresses an experimental observation by intentional misalignment of the optical fiber vertical position with

Figure 3. Quantitative assessment on the FP stability criteria of cylindrical micro-FP cavities translated into the corresponding spectral responses. a) for radius of curvature $R = 300 \mu\text{m}$; $400 \mu\text{m}$; $500 \mu\text{m}$, b) for R ranging from $500 \mu\text{m}$ up to $900 \mu\text{m}$.

respect to the mirrors' axis, as illustrated in **Figure 4**. It is observed from Figure 4a that the experimentally measured spectra differ while tuning the vertical position of the input fiber up and down with respect to the mirror bottom edge. The observed variations are related to transmitted power level, to quality factor and to side mode coupling. This situation can be taken into account in our modeling methodology. Figure 4b shows simulated results of the spectral responses corresponding to intentional misalignment of the fiber vertical position displaced

along the y -axis by a quantity (Δy). Figure 4c shows the corresponding variation of the quality factor versus (Δy) position varied up to $50 \mu\text{m}$. It is observed that there is an optimum position for the fiber vertical position at $\Delta y_B = 25 \mu\text{m}$, at point B, which corresponds to an alignment of the fiber with respect to the center of the mirror. The experimental results of Figure 4a show similar trend while moving the fiber vertical position along the three different positions A, B, and C, corresponding to (Δy) = 20, 25, and $45 \mu\text{m}$, respectively. **Table 1** summarizes the values of

Figure 4. Analysis of the effect of misalignment of the spot with respect to the FP mirrors of similar dimensions; a) experimentally measured spectral transmittance; b) simulated spectral transmittance; c) variation of the fundamental mode Q -factor as a function of the fiber vertical misalignment Δy .

Table 1. Quality factor comparison for misaligned input fiber.

	Experimental		Simulation model	
	FWHM [nm]	Q	FWHM [nm]	Q
Position A - $\Delta\gamma_A = 20 \mu\text{m}$	0.29	5346	0.1684	9205
Position B - $\Delta\gamma_B = 25 \mu\text{m}$	0.27	5742	0.1671	9290
Position C - $\Delta\gamma_C = 45 \mu\text{m}$	0.455	3408	0.1755	8830

the quality factors obtained from measured and simulated spectra. As discussed before, it is admitted that the measured values are always lower than the simulated ones because of the mirror fabrication nonidealities like surface roughness and verticality.

The optical setup used for the measurements is shown in **Figure 5**. It consists of an Agilent–Keysight tunable laser source (TLS) module 81 949 A used to inject the laser light, and 81634B Agilent–Keysight module as an optical power meter to measure the transmitted light. THORLABS single mode fiber P3-SMF28Y-FC-2 is used to collect the light transmitted through the device and to couple it directly to the optical power meter. The Single mode fibers have a spot size of $10.4 \mu\text{m}$. Six axis positioners were used to align each fiber in the input and output grooves. All elements are mounted on an optical table to reduce vibration effects.

3. Analytical Modeling Methodology

In this section, the proposed analytical modeling methodology is described along with details of its implementation. The resulting refined model of Fabry–Pérot cavities is intended primarily to accommodate for any reduction in the mirrors' dimensions. It can also accommodate to any shape and size of the incident light. The outputs of the model are 1) the mode shapes of the resonant modes and 2) the full spectral response of the cavity including resonant wavelength as well as a quantification of the corresponding quality factors. Notably, all these information is obtained here from analytical formalism, while it usually necessitates numerical modeling. It is also worth mentioning that numerical modeling of (sub)millimeter scale FP cavities is very challenging considering the requirement of subwavelength meshing, which translates into extremely large number of elements.

Figure 5. Schematic illustration for the measurement setup.

3.1. Analytical Reconstruction of the Cavity Electromagnetic Field

The proposed modeling idea consists of circulating the electric field between the two reflecting mirrors—or surfaces—considering reflection and transmission at each mirror. The round-trip circulation sequence is executed in an iterative manner and terminates based on convergence criteria as described hereafter. The model takes into account the shape and size characteristics of the incident light as well as the borders of the mirrors of finite dimensions.

As an illustration, our modeling has been implemented in the case of micromirrors of cylindrical shapes submitted to an incident Gaussian beam. In this case, the input parameters for the model are: 1) cavity length L and mirror curvature R ; 2) waist spot size $2w_0$ of the incident Gaussian beam and its location; 3) mirror reflectance (r) and transmittance (t) coefficients as a function of wavelength. Regarding the mirrors, Bragg mirror based on silicon–air multilayers are considered. The corresponding functions $r(\lambda)$ and $t(\lambda)$ are extracted from well-established models available in literature^[4,48] that we adapted. Notably, both r and t are revised to consider the curvature of the mirror and the mirror truncation.

The sequence of this model is summarized in the next steps and illustrated in **Figure 6**. The incident field is a Gaussian beam, typical of the output of an optical fiber. It is defined in spatial domain $E_{\text{incident}}(x, y)$ considering intensity distribution across the mirror where x, y are the transverse axes of the mirror plane and z -axis is the propagation direction as illustrated in Figure 6. In step 1, both the transmitted and reflected fields $E_{\text{Trans.1}}(x, y)$ & $E_{\text{Ref.1}}(x, y)$ are calculated at Mirror 1 using the electric field transmission and reflection coefficients r_1, t_1 . In step 2, the field propagation from Mirror1 to Mirror2 is modeled by implementing Fourier optics model as follows

1) the electric field is transformed from spatial domain to frequency domain using 2D Fast Fourier transform (FFT) operation

$$E(x, y) \xrightarrow{\text{FFT}} A(k_x, k_y) \quad (7)$$

2) Multiplying by propagation factor $e^{-i*n*L*k_z}$ produces the propagated field in frequency domain

$$A_{\text{Prop.}}(k_x, k_y) = A(k_x, k_y) * e^{-i*n*L*k_z} \quad (8)$$

where n is the refractive index of the space between the mirrors and L is the cavity length—or the distance between the two mirrors-, and $k_z = \sqrt{k^2 - (k_x^2 + k_y^2)}$ where k is the wave number ($k = 2\pi/\lambda$).

3) the propagated field is defined back in spatial domain by 2D inverse FFT operation (IFFT)

$$A_{\text{Prop.}}(k_x, k_y) \xrightarrow{\text{IFFT}} E_{\text{Prop.}}(x, y) \quad (9)$$

In step 3, both transmitted and reflected fields $E_{\text{Trans.2}}(x, y)$ & $E_{\text{Ref.2}}(x, y)$ are calculated at Mirror2 using the electric field transmission and reflection coefficients r_2, t_2 . Then, in order to close one iteration of a full round-trip propagation, we consider first, in step 4, the field propagation back from Mirror2 to Mirror1, which is applied by implementing the same Fourier optics formalism

Figure 6. Proposed analytical modeling methodology.

described above and considering back propagation. After that, in step 5, both transmitted and reflected fields $E_{\text{Round Trip}}(x, y)$ and $E_{\text{Ref-Round Trip}}(x, y)$ are calculated at Mirror1 using the electric field transmission and reflection coefficients r_1, t_1 . Then, $E_{\text{Trans.1}}(x, y) + E_{\text{Round Trip}}(x, y)$ forms the field that will propagate in the next iteration.

Notably, the proposed approach enables reconstruction of both the intracavity and the extracavity electromagnetic fields, as well as the corresponding transmittance and reflectance spectral of the FP cavity.

3.2. Convergence Criteria

Since the proposed approach involves multiple iterations, we implemented convergence criteria.^[51] Basically, convergence conditions are intended to decide whether to continue with a new iteration cycle or to terminate the iterations and settle on the final result of the electromagnetic field.

(a) Standard convergence

The initial field “that will propagate from Mirror1 to Mirror2” is calculated in each iteration where

$$E_{N+1, \text{Initial}}(x, y) = E_{\text{Trans.1}}(x, y) + E_{N, \text{Round Trip}}(x, y) \quad (10)$$

and N is the iteration number. Then, a convergence factor (δ) is calculated based on this initial field for both the previous and current iterations.

$$\delta = \sqrt{\frac{\sum (E_{N+1, \text{Initial}}^* - E_{N, \text{Initial}}^*)(E_{N+1, \text{Initial}} - E_{N, \text{Initial}})}{\sum E_{N+1, \text{Initial}}^* E_{N+1, \text{Initial}}}} \quad (11)$$

where $E_{N+1, \text{Initial}}^*$ & $E_{N, \text{Initial}}^*$ are complex conjugate. A certain threshold value is defined for (δ), for example, 0.01 or 0.001,

where the smaller is better to reach steady state. However, smaller value of (δ) leads to greater number of iterations.

(b) Accelerated convergence

In this case, an estimation is made for the new initial field based on the current field and the field after one round trip in the form of linear combination

$$E_{N+1, \text{Initial}} = a_N E_N + b_N E'_{N+1, \text{Initial}} \quad (12)$$

where a_N and b_N are the linear combination coefficients and

$$E'_{N+1, \text{Initial}} = E_{\text{Trans.1}} + E_{N, \text{Round Trip}} \quad (13)$$

The expected error eventually takes the following form

$$\Delta = MX - E_{\text{Trans.1}} \quad (14)$$

where

$$X = \begin{pmatrix} a_N \\ b_N \end{pmatrix} \text{ and } M = \begin{pmatrix} E_N + E_{N, \text{Round Trip}} \\ E'_{N+1, \text{Initial}} - E'_{N+1, \text{Round Trip}} \end{pmatrix}^T \quad (15)$$

The factors a_N and b_N are obtained by solving the following equation

$$X = \left(\sum M^+ M \right)^{-1} \left(\sum M^+ E_{\text{Trans.1}} \right) \quad (16)$$

where M^+ is Hermitian transpose of M .

4. Modeling Validation

4.1. Full Reconstruction of the FP Spectral Response and Mode Shapes

Here, we start first with rather large mirror dimensions compared to the spot size, targeting the validation of our modeling methodology by comparison with analytical formulas that are known to hold true in case of such large mirror's dimensions. A comparison with experimental data is also considered hereafter in this model validation process. For this purpose, we selected a micro-FP cavity with mirror dimensions of $X=150$ and $Y=100\ \mu\text{m}$ submitted to an incident Gaussian beam of beam waist $\omega_0 = 12.5\ \mu\text{m}$ typical of the output of a single mode fiber. **Figure 7** gives the results of our modeling methodology applied to this specific configuration.

Figure 7a shows the spectral response of the FP cavity around a central wavelength of 1550 nm, revealing multiple resonant peaks related to the fundamental mode TEM_{00} and the higher order side modes TEM_{20} and TEM_{40} . The corresponding values of resonance wavelengths and quality factors can be retrieved from this kind of spectrum. Notably, only the even integer values 0, 2, and 4 of the mode orders are observed because of the symmetry of the cylindrical

mirrors and symmetry of the incident Gaussian beam. Higher-order values above 4 cannot be seen here as they are attenuated. Figure 7b, 3c, and 3 d show the spatial distribution of the electric field for those three modes TEM_{00} , TEM_{20} , and TEM_{40} , respectively.

4.2. Model Validation by Comparison with Experimental Data and Applicable Theoretical Equations

(a) Resonance wavelengths

Here, we continue our model validation on large mirrors, considering first, the resonance wavelengths for mode TEM_{00} , TEM_{20} , and TEM_{40} . In **Tables 2** and **3**, we compare the values given by the simulations, with data obtained from experimental results, as well as those obtained from theoretical Equation (4) and (5). Table 2. shows the comparison considering experimental data from a previous report of our group measurements^[44] for cavities with cavity length $L = 210\ \mu\text{m}$ and cylindrical mirrors of height $Y = 77\ \mu\text{m}$, width $X = 125\ \mu\text{m}$ and radius of curvature $R = 140\ \mu\text{m}$. Table 3 shows the comparison considering experimental data from another set of recently measured cavities FP cavity of length $L = 998.5\ \mu\text{m}$ and cylindrical mirrors of height $Y = 150\ \mu\text{m}$, width $X = 200\ \mu\text{m}$ and radius of curvature $R = 800\ \mu\text{m}$.

Figure 7. Full reconstruction of the FP spectral response and mode shapes.

Table 2. Resonance wavelength comparisons for cavity with length 210 μm .

		Mode orders [m,n,q]				
		q = 270	q = 271	q = 272	q = 273	q = 274
Theoretical Equation (4)	(0,0,q)	–	–	1540.34	1534.71	1529.13
	(2,0,q)	1544.12	1538.46	1532.85	–	–
Simulation model	(0,0,q)	–	–	1542.37	1536.91	1531.31
	(2,0,q)	1540.44	1534.99	1529.41	–	–
		q = 274	q = 275	q = 276	q = 277	q = 278
Experimental	(0,0,q)	–	–	1540.6	1535	1529.5
	(2,0,q)	1543.9	1538	1532.4	–	–

Table 3. Resonance wavelength comparisons for cavity with length 998.5 μm .

		Mode orders [m,n,q]			
		q = 1286	q = 1287	q = 1288	q = 1289
Theoretical Equation (4)	(0,0,q)	–	1550.9718	1549.7682	1548.5664
	(2,0,q)	1550.7796	1549.5762	–	–
Simulation model	(0,0,q)	–	1551.2659	1550.0830	1548.8809
	(2,0,q)	1551.0729	1549.9099	–	–
		q = 1288	q = 1289	q = 1290	q = 1291
Experimental	(0,0,q)	–	1551.58	1550.43	1549.22
	(2,0,q)	1551.12	1549.94	–	–

(b) Free spectral range and effective cavity length

In this part, the free spectral range (FSR) is obtained from experimental spectra by measuring the spacing between the resonant peaks of two successive modes TEM_{00} of incremental values of q . Similar procedure is adopted to retrieve the FSR from the spectra given by our simulation model. The corresponding theoretical values of the FSR can be obtained directly from Equation (3) to (4). **Table 4** summarizes those comparison based on the two FP cavities considered in the previous section. From the spectrum in both experimental and simulation model results, the cavity effective lengths are retrieved from the values of the FSR based on Equations (4) and (5) by substituting the FSR value, mirror curvature and the mode order (0,0,q). Hence, the calculated cavity length will express the L_{eff} value. The mode order (0,0,q) was selected based on checking the mode order of the nearest resonance peak obtained from Equation (4) to (5) as well as getting the best fitted FSR which was highlighted in Table 4 through FSR mismatch which is calculated with respect to theoretical value for FSR. Notably, we get a small positive mismatch between the a priori known physical length L of the cavities ($L_{\text{phy}} = 210 \mu\text{m}$ and $L_{\text{phy}} = 998.5 \mu\text{m}$) and the corresponding values L_{eff} obtained through the experimental and simulation model results as shown in Table 4.

The mismatch between L_{phy} and L_{eff} can be explained first by the concept of cavity effective length, where the electric field penetrates the silicon mirrors while circulating back and forth

Table 4. Comparison of FSR, cavity lengths, and effective lengths.

Physical Length L_{phy} [μm]		FSR [nm]	FSR mismatch [%]	Effective Length L_{eff} [μm]
210	Theoretical Equation (4)	5.5876	–	–
	Simulation model	5.595	–0.1	210.281 with [q] values (273 & 274)
	Experiment	5.5	1.6	212.797 with [q] values (277 & 278)
998.5	Theoretical Equation (4)	1.2018	–	–
	Simulation model	1.202	–0.0	998.698 with [q] values (1288 & 1289)
	Experiment	1.201	0.1	999.416 with [q] values (1289 & 1290)

inside the cavity. Notably, for the cavity of $L_{\text{phy}} = 210 \mu\text{m}$, the mismatch between L_{eff} and L_{phy} is higher from experimental data as compared to the simulation model. This can be explained from the underetching that occurs during fabrication, which is translated into an increase of the actual physical length. The latter appears as an additional effect to the electric field penetration inside the silicon mirrors. It is worth noting that the relative variation $(L_{\text{eff}} - L_{\text{phy}})/L_{\text{phy}}$ is more important for the shortest cavities of 210 μm , which is understandable as the optical thickness of the Bragg mirrors becomes less negligible compared to the shortest values of the cavity physical length L_{phy} .

(c) Quality factor and finesse values

The quality factor was also considered as a key parameter for model validation, especially as there is no analytical formula that could be used to determine the quality factor, while the proposed model enables its determination. It can be evaluated directly from the spectral response like the one shown in Figure 7a by just considering the resonance wavelength and full width half maximum: $Q = \lambda_{\text{central}}/\text{FWHM}$. The model gives a quality factor $Q = 2407$ while experiments give $Q = 665$ for the above cavity of length $L = 210 \mu\text{m}$. Notably, even though the orders of magnitude are quite similar, the value of Q obtained from the simulation model is larger than the experimental value because of the nonidealities not considered in our model such as mirror fabrication defects including Bragg layer thicknesses, surface roughness, mirror verticality, and fiber misalignment with respect to the mirror axis. It is important to note that the main root cause of energy loss in small FP cavities is not only related to the mirrors' reflectance as described in Equation (1). Here, after each round-trip within the cavity, a portion of energy leaves the cavity whose lateral dimensions are too small to keep the light confinement. In this case, Equation (1) can be revised by introducing an intracavity attenuation coefficient per unit length α and the corresponding intracavity round-trip loss $\gamma = e^{-2\alpha L}$.^[44]

Figure 8. Quality factor Q as a function of L for different values of the intracavity attenuation coefficient per unit length α . a) for mirror's reflectance $R = 72\%$; b) for mirror's reflectance $R = 99\%$.

$$Q = \frac{2\pi L}{\lambda_0} \left(\frac{\sqrt{\sqrt{e^{-2\alpha L}} R}}{1 - \sqrt{e^{-2\alpha L}} R} \right) \quad (17)$$

It is clear from Equation (17) that the quality factor is not directly proportional to the cavity length L anymore, since the intracavity loss is also dependent on L . The trend of the dependence of quality factor as a function of L will be depending on the strength of the intra-cavity attenuation coefficient per unit length α as well as the mirror's reflectance R . This is illustrated in **Figure 8**, where we considered two values of the mirror's reflectance $R = 72\%$ and $R = 99\%$ for plotting Q as a function of L for different values of α . The particular case of $\alpha = 0$ corresponds to a diffraction lossless cavity, where the linear dependence of Equation (1) holds true.

Besides the quality factor Q , the finesse F is another indicator of the cavity spectral selectivity and of the electromagnetic field enhancement

$$F = \frac{\text{FSR}}{\text{FWHM}} \quad (18)$$

When looking to the finesse numbers, the cavity of length $L = 210 \mu\text{m}$ gives experimental and model values of 2.35 and 8.78, respectively. Similarly for the cavity of length $L = 998.5 \mu\text{m}$, experimental finesse varies from 3 to 5 while it is 7.2 from the model. The numbers are quite low for the finesse compared to those of the quality factor. This can be easily understood from another formulation of the finesse as a function of the quality factor $F = Q/q$. In our case, the cavities operate at large values of the fundamental mode order q as shown in Tables 2 and 3, leading to a significant drop in the finesse. Maximizing the finesse would require decreasing the cavity length, which would lead to not only smaller values for q but also higher values for Q since the diffraction loss would be reduced further.

(d) Mode shapes

A final validation of our modeling methodology relates to the mode shapes. Here again, one can make comparison with an analytical formulation of those modes given by Equation (2), which is applicable for FP cavities of large dimensions compared to the spot size. The field distributions given by our simulation model and shown in Figure 7b–d for modes TEM_{00} , TEM_{20} , and TEM_{40} follow the prediction given by Equation (2). Notably, these figures show that the confinement along x -direction is observed while it is not achieved along the y -direction because of the geometry of the cylindrical mirror which is curved in the x -direction and its planar in the y -direction. This results in an elliptical spot instead of a circular one.

5. Conclusion

In this article, a study on Fabry–Perot cavities revealed some consequences of extreme miniaturization. In particular, the regime where the mirror's dimensions become comparable to the spot size revealed drastic impacts on the spectral response and mode profiles of the microcavities. A fully analytical modeling methodology was presented that accounts for the finite borders of the cavity. The analysis focused on the spectrum response, on the Q -factors as well as the spatial distribution of the resonant modes (fundamental and higher order modes). The analysis highlighted imperfect mode confinement as the root cause of the observed behaviors induced by miniaturization. A comparison between model results with experimental results was proposed as a model validation.

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Conflict of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Data Availability Statement

The data that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

Keywords

extreme miniaturizations, Fabry–Perot, Hermite–Gaussian modes, microcavity devices, micro-optical devices, nonspherical mirror surfaces

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